

Synthesis and characterization of platinumacyclosulfides derived from platinum based heterobimetallic carbonyl clusters

Chinduluri Sravani^a, Sadhana Venkatesh^a, H. Madhesan^a, Kari Vijayakrishna^a, Cherukuri Aswanikumar^b and Akella Sivaramakrishna^{*a}

^aChemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : askrishna@vit.ac.in

^bSchool of Information Technology, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract : The present paper describes the synthesis and reactivity of platinum based trinuclear carbonyl clusters of the type $L_2PtRu_2(CO)_8$ where $L_2 = 1,3$ -bis(diphenylphosphino)propane (dppp) and 1,2-bis(diphenylphosphino)butane (dppe). Reaction of these trinuclear clusters with elemental sulfur yielded the unexpected formation of platinumacyclosulfides. The products were isolated and identified as platinumacyclodisulfide and platinumacyclotetrasulfide by analytical and spectroscopic techniques.

Keywords : Heterobimetallic carbonyl clusters, reactivity, elemental sulfur.

Introduction

A variety of mixed-metal clusters with interesting structural features are known due to their catalytic and synergistic properties¹. This has led further for the synthesis of nano-catalysts with desirable characteristics². Among them platinum based mixed-metallic carbonyls are interesting class of clusters³ and the methods for the synthesis of Pt based heterobimetallic clusters were well described in the past⁴. Various reactivity aspects of these clusters were discussed earlier through either splitting the larger clusters into smaller or aggregation of smaller clusters⁵. In addition to the intramolecular rearrangements and dynamic fluxionality within clusters, several ligand substitution and/or addition reactions were reported with various donor molecules such as phosphines, diphosphines, thioethers, carbonyls, 1,5-cyclooctadiene (COD), alkynyls, vinylidenes etc.³. We have recently described a facile route for the high yield synthesis of mixed trinuclear metal carbonyl clusters of the type $[PtRu_2(CO)_8L_2]$ ($L = PPh_3$; $L_2 = dppe$ or $dppp$) using the reaction of $[Ru_3(CO)_{12}]$ with $[PtL_2(1-alkenyl)_2]$ ⁶ (Scheme 1). The present paper describes the reactions of elemental sulfur with the heterotrinuclear carbonyl clusters as shown in eq. (1).

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All reactions and manipulations were carried out under an inert atmosphere of dry nitrogen using standard Schlenk and vacuum-line techniques. $[Pt(COD)Cl_2]$ ⁷ (COD = 1,5-cyclooctadiene), $[Pt(dppp)Cl_2]$ (dppp = 1,3-bis(diphenylphosphino)propane) and $[Pt(dppp)\{(CH_2)_3CH=CH_2\}_2]$ (1)⁸ were prepared as previously described. $[Ru_3(CO)_{12}]$ (Sigma-Aldrich) was purchased and used as received. The solvents were purchased from commercially available sources and distilled from dark purple solutions of sodium/benzophenoneketyl prior of using. Elemental sulfur was purchased from Alfa Aesar. $[PtRu_2(CO)_8(dppp)]$ (3) was prepared as reported earlier⁹.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy :

¹H and ³¹P NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DXM-400 spectrometer. All ¹H chemical shifts are reported to the residual proton resonance in the deuterated solvent used. All ³¹P chemical shifts are ¹H decoupled and referenced to an 85% phosphoric acid external reference at 0 ppm.

Scheme 1

Elemental analysis :

Micro analyses were conducted with a Thermo Flash 1112 Series CHNS-O Analyzer instrument.

Mass spectrometry :

Mass spectral data was obtained using VG70SE with 8 KV acceleration and the FAB gun is an Iontech Saddlefield, using xenon gas and operating at 8 KV. All matrices were made with 3-nba (3-nitrobenzyl alcohol).

Procedure for the preparation of $(dppp)PtS_2$ (**5**) and $(dppp)PtS_4$ (**6**) :

A solution of $[PtRu_2(CO)_8(dppp)]$ (212 mg, 0.2050 mmol) and elemental sulfur (79 mg, 0.308 mmol) were taken in THF (10 mL) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 18 h. Then the solvent was removed *in vacuo*, and the products were isolated from a preparative TLC plate as two different yellowish brown bands in the presence of CH_2Cl_2 as an eluent and recrystallized from *n*-hexane/ CH_2Cl_2 (5 : 1) at $T = 0^\circ C$. These bands were isolated as major products and dried under

vacuo for 3 h. The isolated products were identified as **5** and **6**. For **5** : Yield : 30 mg (22%), m.p. $154-156^\circ C$ (dec.), Anal. Calcd. for $C_{27}H_{26}P_2S_2Pt$: C, 48.28; H, 3.90; S, 9.55. Found : C, 48.16; H, 3.92; S, 9.49; 1H NMR : δ 7.36–7.92 (20H, m, Ph), 1.82–2.68 (6H, m, P- CH_2); ^{31}P NMR : δ 5.36 (s) (2714 Hz). For **6** : Yield : 45 mg (30%), m.p. $174-178^\circ C$ (dec.), Anal. Calcd. for $C_{27}H_{26}P_2S_4Pt$: Found : C, 44.07; H, 3.56; S, 17.43. Found : C, 44.16; H, 3.62; S, 17.47; 1H NMR : δ 7.28–7.85 (20H, m, Ph), 1.90–2.70 (6H, m, P- CH_2); ^{31}P NMR : δ 5.4 (s) (2706 Hz).

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

As several research groups have extensively studying the synthesis as well as interesting reactivity patterns of platinum based clusters¹⁰, we have recently reported a facile and high yield synthesis of platinum based trinuclear heterobimetallic carbonyl clusters⁶ using bis(1-alkenyl) Pt^{II} complexes as precursors¹¹. Initially bis(1-alkenyl)-

platinum(II) complexes (**1**, **2**) were prepared by the reaction of L_2PtCl_2 where $L_2 = dppp, dppe$ with 1-pentenyl Grignard reagent ($RMgBr$ where $R = 1\text{-pentenyl}$) (Scheme 1) [**11i, j**]. The trinuclear carbonyl cluster with a $\{PtRu_2\}$ core $[L_2PtRu_2(CO)_8]$ (where $L_2 = dppp$ (**3**)) was obtained as products upon the reactions of **1** with $Ru_3(CO)_{12}$ ⁶. A variety of reactions have been reported with Pt-Ru heterobimetallic clusters³. Usually, these clusters are vulnerable to undergo oxidation and form L_2PtI_2 immediately after adding iodine in solution. One of these reactions is the substitution of labile CO ligands with various other ligands.

Reaction with elemental sulfur :

The compounds with Pt-S bonds were reported earlier, but most of the compounds were either ionic or polysulfide compounds^{12,13}. The reaction of elemental sulfur with the title compounds was aimed to form the new clusters with sulfur bridging between Ru and Pt metal centers. However, the reaction did not yield the expected, but produced a mixture of products of platinacyclopoly-

sulfides. ³¹P NMR of the reaction mixture clearly showed several singlets, which are close to each other and similar J_{Pt-P} values. Mass spectral data of the crude reaction mixture exhibited the presence of mass fragments with different platinacyclosulphides i.e. $L_2PtS_6, L_2PtS_5, L_2PtS_4, L_2PtS_3$ and L_2PtS_2 (where $L_2 = dppp$) (Fig. 1). The only products isolated from the crude reaction mixture were confirmed as platinacyclodisulfide, $PtS_2(dppp)$ (**5**) and platinacyclotetrasulfide, $PtS_4(dppp)$ ⁶ as shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The mass spectrum of **5** shows the molecular ion (m/z 670.6) of platinadisulfide and the corresponding fragment with m/z 606.7 for $[(dppp)Pt]^+$ species. The formation of platinacyclotetrasulfide, $PtS_4(dppp)$ (**6**) agrees with the literature reports as the elemental sulfur, S_8 exists as S_4 or S_5 in polar solvents like tetrahydrofuran¹⁴. The spectroscopic data of compound **6** closely agrees with the literature report¹³.

Formal concept Analysis (FCA) is a data analysis technique originated from partial ordering and lattice theory¹⁵⁻¹⁷. In the recent past, few investigations were

Fig. 1. Mass spectral evidence for the formation of platinacyclopolsulfides in reaction mixture.

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum of platinumacyclodisulfide (11).

Fig. 3. Molecular ion of platinumacyclodisulfide (11).

reported in the literature applying FCA to study the complex relationship between fragments in active compounds¹⁸ and to detect the active compounds against different target families in biologically annotated databases¹⁹. Based on these observations, the mass spectral data can further be analyzed using FCA to understand the fragmentation of platinumacyclodisulfides. Molecular FCA indicates the systematic comparison for the formation of different sizes of

platinumacyclodisulfide rings under varied experimental conditions²⁰.

Conclusion

Platinum based trinuclear carbonyl clusters of the type $L_2PtRu_2(CO)_8$ where $L_2 = 1,3$ -bis(diphenylphosphino)propane (dppp) and 1,2-bis(diphenylphosphino)butane (dppe) react with elemental sulfur to yield a mixture of

platinacyclosulfides. Platinacyclodisulfide and platinacyclo-tetrasulfide were isolated and identified as products by analytical and spectroscopic techniques.

Acknowledgement

Dr. ASRK is highly grateful to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR, New Delhi, India) (Ref. No. 01(2451)/11/EMR-II) for the financial support. Our sincere thanks are due to DST-VIT-FIST and SIF-VIT for NMR facilities. Chinduluri Sravani is grateful to VIT University for the research associate fellowship. Mr. Venkatesh Sadhana is thankful to CSIR for the Junior Research Fellowship.

References

- (a) S. Hermans, R. Raja, J. M. Thomas, B. F. G. Johnson, G. Sankar and D. Gleeson, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2001, **7**, 1211; (b) D. S. Shephard, T. Maschmeyer, G. Sankar, J. M. Thomas, D. Ozkaya, B. F. G. Johnson, R. Raja, R. D. Oldroyd and R. G. Bell, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1998, **7**, 1214.
- T. Khimyak and B. F. G. Johnson, *J. Clust. Sci.*, 2004, **15**, 543.
- A. Sivaramakrishna, B. C. E. Makhubela, H. S. Clayton and J. R. Moss, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **252**, 1460.
- M. I. Bruce, J. G. Matison, B. W. Skelton and A. H. White, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1982, **35**, 687; (b) M. I. Bruce, M. R. Snow and E. R. T. Tiekink, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1986, **39**, 2145.
- R. D. Adams, G. Chen, J. G. Wang and W. Wu, *Organometallics*, 1990, **9**, 1339.
- C. Sravani, S. Venkatesh, A. Sivaramakrishna, K. Vijayakrishna, H. S. Clayton, J. R. Moss, V. Moberg and H. Su, *Polyhedron*, 2013, **62**, 169.
- (a) A. J. Dent, L. J. Farrugia, A. G. Orpen and S. E. Stratford, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 1456; (b) L. J. Farrugia, N. MacDonald and R. D. Peacock, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1991, 163; (c) R. D. Adams, B. Captain, W. Fu and P. J. Pellechion, *Chem. Commun.*, 2000, 937.
- (a) R. D. Adams, M. P. Pompeo and W. Wu, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 2899 and the references therein; (b) R. D. Adams, M. S. Alexander, I. Arafat and W. Wu, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **30**, 4717; (c) R. D. Adams, G. Chen, J. G. Wang and W. Wu, *Organometallics*, 1990, **9**, 1339 and the references therein.
- (a) H. Liu, C. Song, L. Zhang, J. Zhang, H. Wang and D. P. Wilkinson, *J. Power Sources*, 2006, **155**, 95; (b) B. L. Garcia, B. Captain, R. D. Adams, A. B. Hungria, P. A. Midgley, S. J. M. Thomas and J. W. Weidner, *J. Clust. Sci.*, 2007, **18**, 121.
- (a) J. M. Thomas, B. F. G. Johnson, R. Raja, G. Sankar and P. A. Modgley, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2003, **36**, 20; (b) R. Raja, T. Khimyak, J. M. Thomas, S. Hermans and B. F. G. Johnson, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 2001, 4638; (c) R. Raja, G. Sankar, S. Hermans, D. S. Shephard, S. Bromley, J. M. Thomas, B. F. G. Johnson and T. Maschmeyer, *Chem. Commun.*, 1999, **16**, 1571.
- (a) A. Sivaramakrishna, H. Clayton, C. Kaschula and J. R. Moss, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **251**, 1294; (b) K. Dralle, N. L. Jaffa, T. L. Roex, J. R. Moss, S. Travis, N. D. Watermeyer and A. Sivaramakrishna, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, 3865; (c) A. Sivaramakrishna, H. Su and J. R. Moss, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 2007, **46**, 3541; (d) T. Mahamo, F. Zheng, A. Sivaramakrishna, G. S. Smith and J. R. Moss, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2008, **693**, 103; (e) A. Sivaramakrishna, H. Su and J. R. Moss, *Dalton Trans.*, 2008, 2228; (f) F. Zheng, A. Sivaramakrishna and J. R. Moss, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2008, **361**, 2871; (g) A. Sivaramakrishna, H. Su and J. R. Moss, *Organometallics*, 2007, **26**, 5786; (h) A. Sivaramakrishna, B. C. E. Makhubela, G. S. Smith and J. R. Moss, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2010, **695**, 1627; (i) A. Sivaramakrishna, J. R. Moss and H. Su, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2010, **363**, 3345; (j) A. Sivaramakrishna, B. C. E. Makhubela, F. Zheng, H. Su and J. R. Moss, *Polyhedron*, 2008, **27**, 44.
- (a) K.-W. Kim and M. G. Kanatzidis, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1993, **32**, 4163; (b) S. Ford, M. R. Lewtas, C. P. Morley and M. Di Vaira, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2000, 933.
- (a) J. Chatt and D. M. P. Mingos, *J. Chem. Soc., Sect. A*, 1970, 1243; (b) R. R. Gukathasan, R. H. Morris and A. Walker, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1983, **61**, 2490.
- F. A. Cotton, G. Wilkinson, C. A. Murillo and M. Bochmann, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 6th ed., Wiley-Interscience, John Wiley & Sons, 1999, p. 534.
- B. Ganter and R. Wille, "Formal Concept Analysis : Mathematical Foundations", Springer, 1999.
- Ch. Aswani Kumar, "Mining association rules using non-negative matrix factorization and formal concept analysis", Proc. of 5th International conference on information processing, Springer CCIS, Vol. 157, 31-39, 2011.
- Ch. Aswani Kumar and S. Srinivas, *Expert Systems with Applications*, 2010, **37**, 2696.
- E. Lounkine, J. Auer and J. Bajorath, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **57**, 5342.
- E. Lounkine, D. Stumpfe and J. Bajorath, *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 2009, **49**, 1359.
- A. Sivaramakrishna, C. Aswanikumar and K. Vijayakrishna, 2014, unpublished results.